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Impact of Demographic and Psychological Variables on Sustainable Consumption Behavior in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa

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ABSTRACT

This study empirically investigated the effects of demographic and psychological variables on sustainable consumption behavior in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Cross-sectional research design was used in this study. A well-structured questionnaire and a multistage sampling approach were used to collect the data, while the sample size was determined following the Krejcie and Morgan method. Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modelling was used to estimate the effects of demographic and psychological variables on sustainable consumption behavior. The findings of the study show that all independent variables of the study, except gender, have statistically significant effects on sustainable consumption behavior. The coefficients of age, education, income, Perceived behavioral Control and Perceived Environmental Responsibility are positive, which means that increase in age, education level, income, Perceived behavioral control and perceived environmental responsibility make consumers more sustainable in consumption. The positive coefficient of gender demonstrates that female consumers are more sustainable in consumption than male consumers, however the difference between male and female in sustainable consumption are statistically insignificant. The coefficient of employment status is negative which means that employed consumers are more sustainable in consumption than the unemployed consumers. Finally, this study put forward some valuable recommendations for stimulating sustainable consumption behavior to policy makers and businesses.

Key words: Sustainable Consumption Behavior, Demographic Variables, Psychological Variables, PLS-SEM

Introduction

Traditional consumption pattern has created many hurdles for achievement of sustainable consumption. The overconsumption of natural resources and excessive amounts of waste generated by unsustainable consumption patterns has adversely affected the achievement of environmental aspect of sustainability (Arora & Mishra, 2023). In fact, unsustainable production and consumption make the triple planetary crises of climate change, biodiversity loss and pollution more severe (Guo & Yang, 2024). These disastrous consequences of unsustainable consumption impede social and economic progress along

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their impacts on ecosystems and consequently, hamper the achievement of sustainable development goals (Rasheed et al., 2025). There is an urgent need to replace unsustainable consumption which weakens the ability of future generations to satisfy their needs with sustainable consumption which can provide a smooth trajectory to achievement of sustainable development goals (Arora & Mishra, 2023).

Sustainable consumption is globally considered a potential solution to the problems created by unsustainable consumption behavior. It is recognized as a key driver for execution of sustainable development strategies, aligning their daily consumption pattern with long term environmental well-being (Guo & Yang, 2024). By transforming from linear economy model of Take-Make-Dispose, the sustainable consumption patterns emphasize the efficient utilization of resources, reduction of waste and adaptation of responsible production processes such as promoting circular economy practices, energy conservation, and encouraging innovations which facilitate production of sustainable products (Fatima et al., 2020). In this way, sustainable consumption can remove all the menaces created by unsustainable consumption. It can mitigate climate change, control the depletion of natural resources, and ensure equitable use of resources. Sustainable consumption and production are imperative for countries like Pakistan where rapid population increase and unplanned development results in excessive environmental degradation and obstructs the sustainable development (Glavič, 2021). Hence, environmental protection can be ensured, and well-being of overall society can be increased by encouraging sustainable consumption behavior.

Demographic and Psychological variables are important determinants of sustainable consumption behavior. Demographic factors such as age of consumers, gender, education, income and employment status are important drivers of sustainable consumption behavior. These demographic factors affect the behavior and overall preferences of human beings (Rasheed et al., 2025). These factors determine consumers accessibility to resources, increase their environmental awareness and alter their consumption patterns. For example, high levels of education can make consumers aware of the consequences of unsustainable consumption and thus education motivates them to adopt sustainable consumption behavior (Dimitrova et al., 2022). In addition to demographic factors, psychological variables also have crucial role in determining sustainable consumption behavior. Perceived behavioral control, a crucial psychological variable, is an individual's belief in his or her ability to perform a particular behavior – has a significant effect on sustainable consumption behavior (Salleh et al., 2024). When an individual feels that he can perform a particular behavior easily, he is more likely to adopt that behavior, hence such person can more easily incline himself towards sustainable consumption behavior (Ayar & Gürbüz, 2021). Likewise, perceived environmental responsibility (PER), which represents one's felt obligation or duty to protect the environment, tends to motivate pro-environmental intentions and purchase decisions (Zheng et al., 2020). Individuals who internalize responsibility for environmental outcomes are more inclined toward sustainable consumption, such as choosing green products or reducing waste (Fabio et al., 2025). Recent research underscores that integrating such psychological factors is vital for explaining and predicting sustainable consumer behavior.

This research study will make some valuable contributions. First, it fills a geographical research gap by investigating the effect of demographic and psychological variables on sustainable consumption behavior in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, a region where sustainable consumption behavior was not examined empirically. By providing area-specific empirical evidence from Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, this study adds valuable empirical

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evidence regarding sustainable consumption behavior in developing countries context. This study investigated the impact of both demographic and two crucial psychological determinants of sustainable consumption behavior in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Second, this study also make a methodological contribution as most of the previous related studies which examined the effects of demographic variables on green consumption behavior and pro-environmental behavior used traditional hypotheses tests such as t test and ANOVA. This study used a Partial Least Square Structural Equation modelling.

Literature Review

The theoretical nexus between age and sustainable consumption behavior is explained by Life Course Theory (LCT). LCT theory states that behavior and choices of consumers are determined by their different roles in life such as transforming towards parental role from non-parental role, gets starting jobs or getting retired and the historical context they live in (Elder Jr. et al., 2003). These factors affect individual behavior overtime. Therefore, it is inferred from LCT theory that sustainable consumption behavior of a person does vary across age groups. Young consumers have more environmental awareness and thus, they adopt more sustainability friendly behavior, however, weak financial position of younger consumers prevents them to adopt sustainable behavior as sustainable products are often expensive (Kadic-Maglajlic et al., 2019). On the other hand, young financial consumers adopt more sustainable behavior due to their strong financial position. Furthermore, older consumers may hold a stronger sense of responsibility regarding environment preservation for their children and future generations (das Neves, 2025). Younger consumers may adopt more sustainable consumption behavior as they have more environmental knowledge. Cottrell (2003) also states that younger consumers adopt more pro-environmental behavior as they are more enthusiastic regarding protection of environment.

The Value–Belief–Norm (VBN) theory postulates that increase in the level of consumers’ education enhances sustainable consumption behavior. VBN theory postulates that consumers holding strong environment related values are more likely to behave sustainable behavior as they understand the negative implications of traditional consumption (Onel, 2024). Education enhances this nexus by increasing a consumer’s awareness and sense of responsibility. When consumers get more knowledge about the environmental consequences of their consumption activities, they start to follow environment related altruistic and bio-spheric values which lead them towards adopting responsible consumption (Çakır Yıldırım & Karaarslan Semiz, 2019). In essence, education has significant role in activating environment related values and thus, motivates consumers to adopt more sustainable practices. It also motivates consumers to follow personal and social norms that guide them to adopt sustainable practices (Xie et al., 2021). People with stronger personal norms will consume in a way which minimizes waste generation, conservation of natural resources and promote sustainable practices. (Čapienè et al., 2022).

The theoretical relationship between sustainable consumption and gender is supported by Socialization theory which states that a consumer learns values related to environmental protection and sustainability from people living in their surroundings such as family, peer groups and educational institution (Godin & Langlois, 2021). This theory states that women have the role of caregiver and nurturing and this role of women encourage them to be more compassionate and empathetic than men, therefore, women adopt more sustainable consumption behavior than men (Blocker & Eckberg, 1997). Female consumers behave more sustainable in consumption activities such as purchasing clothes,

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cleaning and cooking (Bloodhart & Swim, 2020). Socialization Theory also states that male consumers adopt more sustainable behavior as they perform the role of economic provider and involve in market activities such as home renovation and buying energy efficient home appliance (Brough et al., 2016). Male decides more rationally due to his role of economic provider and therefore, male consumers behave more sustainable than women. In nutshell, Socialization Theory postulates that both male and female consumers can be sustainable in consumption and empirical studies also demonstrates mixed results.

Value-Belief-Norm theory supports a positive relationship between consumers' income and sustainable consumption behavior. This theory states that values, beliefs and norms affect sustainable consumption behavior of a person and income empowers a consumer to follow values, beliefs and norms (Stern, 2000). Hence, a rise in consumer income enables consumers to consume sustainably. VBN theory postulates that biospheric values highlight the importance of environmental protection and altruistic values lead a person to be concerned about the welfare of coming generations (Gomes et al. 2022). A rise in consumers' income increases his affordability and enables a person to follow personal norms related to sustainable behavior and thus enhances sustainable behavior. Beliefs, a second aspect of VBN theory, also lead him to behave more sustainably. A person's belief regarding adverse effects of his unsustainable consumption behavior motivates him to consume sustainable products and his higher income enables him to buy sustainable products. Personal norms, a third aspect of VBN theory, make a person environmentally responsible and a norm follower consumer is more likely to adopt sustainable consumption behavior and a rise in consumers' income makes it easy for him to follow sustainability related norms as a rise in income increases his purchasing power and he can afford expensive sustainable products.

The relationship of sustainable consumption behavior with employment status is supported by Social Learning Theory which states that an individual behavior is influenced by his observation of other people. Social learning theory states that individuals learn about environmentally friendly and sustainable practices and then follow these practices in their daily lives. Hence, workplace is considered a factor which makes consumers sustainable in consumption. Employment can also lead a person towards adaptation of unsustainable consumption as employment boosts his or her purchasing power and leads a person to over-consumption and consequently his or her over-consumption generates waste and pollutes the environment (Cohen & Winn, 2007). Unemployed people can also be more sustainable in consumption as some sustainability related behavior such as pro-environmental behavior need time and unemployed people have more time to perform pro-environmental behavior (Clerk et al., 2003).

Perceived Behavioral Control refers to the beliefs of a person about the ease or difficulty of executing that behavior (Ajzen, 2020). The theory of planned behavior (TPB) explains the relationship between Perceived Behavioral Control and sustainable consumption behavior. This theory states that intentions determine behavior of a person but the extent to which intentions may be actualized into definite action depends on two interdependent factors which are perceived controllability of behavior and actual control of executing that behavior (García-Salirrosas et al., 2024). According to TPB, PBC, in addition to attitudes and norms, shapes intentions of a person and when PBC reveals real constraints, it can also directly affect behavior by approximating actual control.

Generally sustainable consumption needs more resources, extra effort and favorable conditions such as required infrastructure and availability of sustainable products (Yuriev et al., 2020). Higher PBC can increase consumers' willingness and ability to consume in

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sustainable manners. Extant empirical studies also demonstrate that PBC accurately predicts green purchase intentions and consumers' willingness to pay more for environmentally friendly goods (Bosnjak et al., 2020; Hagger et al., 2022; La Barbera & Ajzen, 2020).

Perceived Environmental Responsibility (PER) is the individual's sense of moral duty to protect the environment and abstain oneself from harming the environment (Savari et al., 2023). It implies that a person considers himself responsible for environment, understanding that his consumption pattern can affect society and nature. Norm Activation Model (NAM) explains the theoretical relationship between perceived environmental responsibility and sustainable consumption behavior. This theory postulates that personal moral norms lead a person to adopt altruistic and pro-social behavior including environmental actions (Trinh et al., 2025). This theory further adds that personal moral norms are activated by a person's awareness of environmental damage and ascription of personal responsibility for environmental damage (Ai et al., 2024). In the context of sustainable consumption behavior, this implies that a person who understands the negative environmental impacts of unsustainable consumption and preventing negative environmental consequences as his personal responsibility (have high perception of environmental responsibility) will be more likely to adopt sustainable consumption behavior (Fang et al., 2019). The activation of personal norms such as feeling that I can protect environment, encourage an individual to adopt more sustainable practices (Zheng et al., 2020). Thus, perceived environmental responsibility is the stimulator that transforms environmental concerns and knowledge into a sense of obligations to keep his consumption on a tract which assists achieving sustainability (Ai et al., 2024).

Empirical Review

Vicente-Molina et al. (2018) examined gender differences regarding pro-environmental behavior using order logit model and found that women exhibit higher level of pro-environmental behavior than men. Wang et al. (2022) investigated the effect of education level on pro-environmental behavior using instrumental variables methods and two stages least square regression model and found that education has significant positive effect on pro-environmental behavior. Wang et al. (2022) also found that urban residents exhibit more pro-environmental behavior than the rural residents. Xiao and McCright (2014) examined gender differences in pro-environmental behavior using logit model and found that women display more pro-environmental behavior in private sphere whereas men display more pro-environmental behavior in public sphere. Meyer (2015) empirically inspected the effect of education on pro-environmental behavior using two stage least square methods as main estimation technique and his study's results demonstrate that education stimulates pro-environmental behavior. Findings of Meyer (2015) also demonstrate that women exhibit more pro-environmental behavior than men. Du et al. (2024) investigated the relationship of pro-environmental with income using hierarchical regression model and findings of their study demonstrate that higher income level enhances pro-environmental behavior. Díaz et al. (2020) examined the effects of psychological variables on pro-environmental behavior and findings of their study show that environmental attitudes, self-efficacy and trust in sources of environmental knowledge have significant and positive effects on pro-environmental behavior.

Witek and Kuźniar (2020) examined the influence of socio-economic factors on green purchase behavior using Mann-whitney's U test and ANOVA Kruskal-Wallis test for hypotheses testing and found that women are more inclined towards purchase of green

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products than men. Their study also found that younger consumers are less inclined towards green consumption than elder consumers whereas education and personal financial situation have positive influence on green purchasing behavior. Migheli (2021) used Probit regression and Heckman selection method to examine the effects of gender, education and income and the findings of their study demonstrate that these three factors stimulate green consumption behavior. Ibok and George (2014) used correlation matrix to investigate the relationship of green consumption with socio-economic variables i.e., age, gender, education and income and their findings demonstrate positive correlation of green consumption with socio-economic factors. Vistharakula and Kaushik (2021) examined the effects of gender and age on consumers green behavior using t test and correlation and found insignificant relationship of consumer green behavior with gender and age. Mustafa (2007) examined gender differences regarding green consumption behavior of Egyptian citizens using MONOVA as estimation technique and outcome of his study demonstrate that men show more positive attitude towards green consumption than women. Maichum et al. (2016) used Structural equations modelling approach to inspect the determinants of green purchase behavior and their findings demonstrate that perceived behavioral control, subjective norms and consumer have positive and statistically positive effects on green purchase behavior whereas environmental knowledge was found to have insignificant direct effect on green purchase; however, this study found that environmental knowledge affects green purchase behavior through the mediating role of perceived behavioral control, consumer attitudes and subjective norms. Joshi and Rehman (2016) used structural equations modelling approach to inspect the determinants of green purchasing and found that social influence, perceived environmental knowledge, ecolabelling and recycling participation rate have positive influence on green purchase.

Čapienė et al. (2022) examined the effects of internal factors i.e., perceived environmental responsibility, personal norms, environmental attitude and values using spearman's rank correlation technique, Kruskal Wallis test and Mann Whitney U test for hypothesis testing and findings of their study demonstrate that all independent variables of this study have positive influence on sustainable consumption behavior. Dimitrova et al. (2022) employed structural equations modelling approach for investigating the determinants of sustainable consumption behavior and their study reveals that environmental influence and knowledge stimulates sustainable consumption behavior whereas materialism has negative influence on sustainable consumption behavior. Piligrimiene et al. (2020) examined the effects of psychological variables i.e., perceived responsibility and perceived behavioral efficacy on sustainable consumption behavior and found that these mentioned variables increase sustainable consumption practices. Verma (2014) inspected the relationship of sustainable consumption behavior with psychological factors i.e., norms and attitude using MANOVA as main estimation technique and found that that these two psychological factors stimulate sustainable consumption behavior. Minton et al. (2016) used MANOVA to explore the link of sustainable attitude and behavior with pragmatism and outcome of their study demonstrate that pragmatism positively influences sustainable attitude and behavior. The study of Minton et al. (2016) also found that the relationship between pragmatism in society and self-enhancing sustainable behavior is mediated by sustainable attitudes. White and Simpson (2013) used ANOVA to empirically inspect the effects of three types of appeals i.e., injective appeals, descriptive appeals and benefits appeal on sustainable consumption behavior and findings of their study demonstrate that the effects of appeal on sustainable consumption behavior depend on the self-activation at individual and

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collective levels. The findings show that injective and descriptive appeals have more effective role and benefits appeal have less effective role in stimulating sustainable consumption behavior at the time of collective level self-activation whereas self-benefits and descriptive appeals are more effective in enhancing sustainable consumption behavior at a time of individual level self-activation.

Research Methodology

This study employed quantitative research design to explore the impact of demographic and psychological factors on sustainable consumption behavior in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. The dependent variable of this study is Sustainable Consumption Behavior (SCB) which has three dimensions which are quality of life, care for environment and care for future generations. SCB is twenty-four items' indicators developed by Quoquab et al. (2019) and each item was rated by five-point Likert Scale. The independent variables are categorized into two groups i.e., demographic variables and psychological variables. Demographic variables are age, gender, education, household income and employment status. Two important psychological variables are Perceived Behavioral Control and Perceived Environmental Responsibility. The data of income and age was collected through ended questions and after collection of data, these variables were converted as ordinal variables. Gender has two categories i.e., male and female and thus, it was incorporated as dichotomous variable. Education has five levels i.e., illiterate, secondary, higher secondary, Bachelor and Master and above master. Education was also incorporated as ordinal variable as the levels of education have order. Employment status is also a dichotomous variable, and it has two categories. Perceived Behavioral Control was measured by six indicators and Perceived Environmental Responsibility was measured by seven indicators. The indicators/ items of all multi-item (Latent Variables) variables are presented in table 1.

Table 1. Indicators of Latent Variables

Variables	Dimensions	Abbreviation of Items	Items/Indicators
Sustainable Consumption Behavior (SCB)	Quality of Life	SCB1	I always make efforts to reduce the misuse of products.
		SCB2	I always recycle newspapers.
		SCB3	I always try to be mindful in consumption.
		SCB4	I try to avoid over-consumption of products
		SCB5	I always re-use paper to write on the other side of it.
		SCB6	While eating at restaurants, I put up as much as order for food as I can eat to avoid wasting food.
		SCB7	I like to purchase products with biodegradable packaging.
		SCB8	I always avoid wasting food and beverages.
		SCB9	I recycle my old things in every possible manner.
		SCB10	I re-use my shopping bags every

	SCB11	time I go shopping. I do plan mindfully before I buy a good or service.
Care for Environment	SCB12	I do care for the environment.
	SCB13	I use eco-friendly goods and services.
	SCB14	I buy and consume environmental friendly goods and services.
	SCB15	I often pay extra amount to buy environmentally friendly goods and services.
	SCB16	I am mindful of the shortage of natural resources.
	SCB17	I prefer using paper bags as they are biodegradable.
Care For Future Generation	SCB18	I do love the planet.
	SCB19	I always keep in mind that my over-consumption can hinder the ability of future generations to satisfy their basic needs.
	SCB20	I always care about the need fulfillment for future generations.
	SCB21	I am concerned about the quality of life of future generations.
	SCB22	I try to avoid excess consumption for the sake of the next generation.
	SCB23	I am concerned about the future generation.
	SCB24	I try to control my over-consumption to preserve environmental resources for future generations.
	Perceived Behavior Control (PBC)	PBC1
PBC2		You have resources to purchase environmentally friendly products.
PBC3		You have time to search and purchase environmentally friendly products
PBC4		You have willingness to purchase environmentally friendly products
PBC5		There are likely to be plenty of opportunities for you to purchase environment friendly product
PBC6		Being environmentally friendly would be entirely within your control.

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Perceived Environmental Responsibility (PER)	PER1	I should be responsible for protecting our environment.
	PER2	Environmental protection starts with me.
	PER3	I think I have a responsibility in protecting the environment in my country.
	PER4	I have taken responsibility for environmental protection since I was young.
	PER5	I am willing to take up responsibility to protect the environment in my country.
	PER6	Environmental protection is the responsibility of my government, not mine.
	PER7	Environmental protection is the responsibility of the environmental organizations, not mine.

Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, a province of Pakistan, was the target population of this study. This province has seven administrative divisions, i.e., Peshawar, Malakand, Hazara, Mardan, Kohat, Bannu and Dera Ismail Khan. Multi cluster sampling technique was used to collect the data required for this study. In the first stage of sampling, three divisions were selected i.e., Peshawar, Kohat and Malakand, out of total seven divisions. In the second stage, districts were selected from selected divisions. Charsadda, Nowshera, and Peshawar were selected from Peshawar division, Kohat, Hangu and Kurram were selected from Kohat division and Buner, Lower Dir, Swat, and Upper Dir were selected from Malakand division. Finally, respondents were selected from urban and rural areas of selected districts using proportionate sampling. For selecting an appropriate the sample size, the Krejcie and Morgan Table (1970) was employed. This table suggests a sample of 384 respondents as an adequate sample size when the population size is greater than one million (Rahman, 2023).

Structural Equation Models (SEMs) are of two types: one is Covariance-Based SEM (CB-SEM) and the other is Variance-Based SEM, also known as Partial Least Squares SEM (PLS-SEM). PLS-SEM based estimation relies on ordinary least squares (OLS) method, while CB-SEM is estimated using maximum likelihood (ML) approach (Jannoo et al., 2014). The aim of PLS-SEM is to estimate the nexus between variables by minimizing the residual variance of endogenous variable (Hair et al., 2019). In simpler words, it tries to maximize the R square of dependent variable, which demonstrates the achievement of predictive objective by researchers (Rožman et al., 2020). Due to predictive ability of PLS-SEM, it has higher statistical power and is considered more efficient in parameters estimation (Hair et al., 2011). CB-SEM needs normal distribution of data whereas PLS-SEM does not need the normal distribution of data (Kono & Sato, 2023). Variables of different scales and a single item variable can be incorporated in PLS-SEM model. Both these techniques evaluate the quality of through different statistics of reliability, convergent validity, discriminant validity, and path coefficients. However, CB-SEM also relies on indexes of goodness-of-fit, which makes it more complex, whereas PLS-SEM does not need goodness of fit indexes and it is relatively simpler (Hair et al., 2017; Rasheed et al., 2025). therefore, PLS-SEM can be used in

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many situations due to its flexibility, easy to use, and particularly useful for prediction-oriented research. Therefore, this study employed PLS-SEM to estimate the model of this study.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results and discussion of this study. Table 2 presents sample size distribution. It shows the number of observations in each group of all demographic variables. Table 3 displays the results of reliability and validity of multi-item variables. The values of Cronbach Alpha (CA), Composite reliability (CR) and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) are greater than their threshold levels. Therefore, it is concluded that all variables have achieved both reliability and convergent validity.

Table 2. Sample Size Distribution

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Household Income	20000-70000	115	23
	70001-120000	108	21.2
	120001-170000	87	16.6
	170001-220000	98	19.8
	220001-270000	92	19
Employment status (UEMP)	Employed	257	51.4
	Unemployed	243	48.6
Age	18-30	131	26.2
	31-40	134	26.8
	41-50	133	26.6
	51-62	102	20.4
Education	Illiterate	99	19.8
	Secondary	100	20
	Higher secondary	96	19.2
	Bachelor	102	20.4
Gender	Master and above	103	20.6
	Master		
	Male	254	50.8
	Female	246	49.2

Table 3. Reliability and Convergent Validity (PLS-SEM)

Variables	CA	CR	AVE
SCB	0.96	0.96	0.51
PBC	0.88	0.89	0.61
PER	0.94	0.95	0.75

Table 4 presents the result of discriminant validity of multi-item variables of this study. Two tests of discriminant validity i.e., Fornell-Larcker criterion and HTMT ratio demonstrate that discriminant validity of multi-item variables were achieved as all values on main diagonal are greater than values off the main diagonal. The results of HTMT test show that HTMT values of all variables are less than 0.85 which also demonstrates that discriminant validity was achieved.

Table 4. Discriminant Validity

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Fornell-Larcker criterion								
Variables	Age	Education	Gender (Female)	Income	PBC	PER	SCB	UEMP
Age	1.00							
Education	0.10	1.00						
Gender (Female)	0.19	0.21	1.00					
Income	0.17	0.19	-0.07	1.00				
PBC	0.08	0.39	-0.01	0.24	0.78			
PER	0.16	0.39	-0.14	0.30	0.64	0.87		
SCB	0.19	0.42	0.00	0.30	0.69	0.70	0.71	
UEMP	0.07	0.40	0.41	0.12	0.07	0.01	0.05	1.00

HTMT ratio						
Age	Education	Gender (Female)	Income	PBC	PER	SCB
0.10						
0.19	0.21					
0.17	0.19	0.07				
0.09	0.39	0.06	0.25			
0.17	0.40	0.15	0.31	0.68		
0.18	0.42	0.10	0.32	0.78	0.82	
0.07	0.40	0.41	0.12	0.12	0.05	0.09

Table 5 exhibits the results of collinearity statistics. Collinearity was examined by VIF test which shows the absence of multicollinearity problems as the VIF values of all variables are less than the threshold level of 5.

Table 5 Collinearity Statistics (VIF)

Variables	VIF
Age	1.11
Education	1.51
Female	1.35
Income	1.15
PBC	1.79
PER	1.99
UEMP	1.40

Table 6 presents the results of structural model estimated by PLS-SEM. The results show that the coefficient of age is positive and statistically significant ($\beta=0.13$, $P<0.01$) which implies that elder consumers are more sustainable than the younger consumers and level of sustainable consumption of a person increases as his age increases. The positive effect of age on sustainable consumption behavior is supported by the Theory of Life Support which postulates that a person's role changes as his age increases and the change in his role such as becoming a father or mother makes him more caution and hence, he consumes more sustainably. The empirical study conducted by Witek and Kuźniar (2020) corroborates the finding of this study as their study also found a positive effect of

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age on sustainable consumption behavior however the result of the present study contrasts with the findings of Lazaric et al. (2020). The coefficient of education ($\beta=0.36$, $P<0.01$) is positive and statistically significant which implies that increase in the level of education of a consumer makes him more sustainable in consumption. It is also inferred from this finding that more educated consumers are more sustainable in consumption than the less educated consumers.

The coefficient of gender is positive; however, it is statistically insignificant ($\beta=0.4$, $P=0.18$). The positive coefficient implies that female consumers are more sustainable in consumption than male consumers whereas the insignificant coefficient of gender means that the difference between male and female in terms of sustainable consumption behavior is statistically insignificant.

The findings show that increase in income causes improvement in sustainable consumption behavior as the coefficient of income is positive and statistically significant ($\beta=0.20$, $P<0.01$). The positive effect of income on sustainable consumption behavior is supported by Value Belief and Norm (VBN) Theory. VBN theory states that increase in the income of consumers enables him to follow sustainability related values and norms and hence, his level of sustainable consumption increases. Increase in income enables consumers to act open personal norms related to environmental protection (Gomes et al., 2022). Norms following consumers are more likely to consume sustainably as their income increases because increase in income increases their purchasing power and hence, they can consume expensive though sustainable products. The positive effect of income on sustainable consumption behavior found by this study is consistent with the findings of Du et al. (2024) whose research findings demonstrate that high income people adopt more pro-environmental behavior.

The coefficient of employment status (UEMP) is negative and statistically significant ($\beta=-0.25$, $P<0.01$) which implies that employed person is more sustainable in consumption than unemployed person. Social Learning Theory explains the reason behind this result. This theory postulates that a person observes behavior of other people and then changes his behavior accordingly (Wilhite, 2014). The workplace environment is an important place to observe the behavior of all people, and it provides opportunities to observe and learn behavior related to sustainability (Koutroubas & Galanakis, 2022). This finding of the current study is supported by the empirical finding of Hicklenton et al. (2019) which demonstrates that workplace environment enables a person to adopt more pro-environmental behavior.

Table 6. PLS-SEM Structural Model results

Variables	Beta	SD	T Values	P values
Age	0.13	0.05	2.60	0.04
Education	0.36	0.03	13.12	0.00
Gender (Female)	0.04	0.03	1.33	0.18
Income	0.20	0.03	6.66	0.00
UEMP	-0.25	0.09	2.78	0.00
PBC	0.04	0.02	2.00	0.05
PER	0.09	0.04	2.25	0.04

Table 7. Assessment of Model Quality

Variables	R ²	Q ²	f ²
SCB	0.74	0.34	

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Age	0.14
Education	0.23
Gender (Females)	0.03
Income	0.19
UEMP	0.15
PBC	0.19
PER	0.18

Conclusion and Recommendations

The current study was undertaken to empirically inspect the effects of demographic and psychological variables on sustainable consumption behavior in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. Data was collected through well-structured questionnaire from the target population. Multistage cluster sampling technique was used to collect data and KM table was used to determine the sample size. The findings of the study show that both demographic variables and psychological variables have significant role in determining sustainable consumption behavior. The findings show that increase in age of a consumer statistically significant effects enhances levels of sustainable consumption behavior. Increase in the level of income and education foster sustainable consumption behavior. Females are more sustainable in consumption than the male consumers, however the difference is between female consumers and male consumers in term of sustainable consumption behavior is statistically insignificant. The findings further show that the difference between employed person and unemployed person are statistically significant and employed person are more sustainable in consumption than the unemployed person. The psychological variables, i.e., perceived environmental responsibility and perceived behavioral control also have statistically significant on sustainable consumption behavior. The present study put forward some valuable suggestions based on the findings of this study. As the study found age and education have positive effects on sustainable consumption behavior, it is recommended that sustainability related programs be initiated for less educated people and illiterate people and these sustainability promotion programs should be integrated in school curriculum as younger consumers are relatively less sustainable in consumption. Furthermore, the current investigation also put forward some valuable suggestions for businesses and marketers. Businesses should produce sustainable products that are mostly consumed by younger consumers. Generally, environmentally friendly and sustainable products are not affordable to low-income consumers and unemployed people as sustainable products are high priced, therefore, firms are suggested to produce less expensive products, and government should subsidize the sustainable products. Unemployed person can be made sustainable by initiating sustainability programs such as repair and reuse workshops and neighborhood cleanliness initiatives.

Limitations and Future Research Direction

Due to time constraints and high cost of collecting data, this empirical investigation was undertaken in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, a relatively small geographical region. Hence, the findings of this investigation cannot be generalized to the entire country. However, the novelty of this study provides a path to future research and future researchers are directed to extend this study to the country and different cultural contexts with financial support from government. Future researchers are suggested to explore the effects of demographic factors and psychological variables on cooperative consumption, other aspects of sustainable consumption behavior.

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